

Visualizing mathematics with the MathBot: a constructionist activity to explore mathematical concepts through robotics

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Abstract (for Research/Practice Papers only, style: Abstract title)

In this practice paper, we aim to share our experience with the design and implementation of constructionist educational robotics activities tailored to primary school students (4th grade, age 9-11 years) implemented in a series of robotics workshops, which took place within a real school setting in Sofia, Bulgaria.

Through this contribution, we will further present an activity plan, which involves student engagement with mathematical concepts (angle measuring and properties of the circle) in order to program the behaviour of a robot. Our paper reports insights on the implementation of the activity plan focusing students' evaluation of their experience during the workshop. These insights are drawn from quantitative data from 131 participants (63 boys and 68 girls), capturing the overall student attitude.

The activity plan behind this set of educational robotics workshops was designed, adapted and piloted in alignment to the guidelines of the Bulgarian national curriculum for mathematics for the 4th grade. However, it could function as a practical example, which could be adapted, enriched and modified to benefit other age groups, nationalities and desired learning outcomes.

Keywords (style: Keywords)

educational robotics; mathematics; programming; Scratch; primary education;

Introduction

The increasing difficulty related to maintaining students' positive attitude and motivation towards the educational process is not a new topic neither for the Bulgarian education scene, nor internationally. Furthermore, against the backdrop of the rapidly changing technological landscape, which demands the continuous improvement of computer science curricula in general education schools, providing students with a functional understanding of how technology works becomes a paramount and a challenge.

The ICT general education in Bulgaria is already undergoing a renaissance of a sort with subjects such as computer modelling¹²³ with Scratch for primary school students being gradually included within the official school curriculum. Furthermore, curriculum strategies are being developed in order to include a multidisciplinary approach towards learning, an example being the Ministry of Education's "Innovative Schools"⁴⁵⁶ initiative granting schools a certain level of curriculum flexibility and allowing them to include innovative learning approaches and multidisciplinary subjects.

At the same time, there is a worldwide turn to robotics and STEM education alike, with a big number of robotics kits launched during the last few years. According to the International Federation of Robotics in October 2016, from 2014 to 2015, unit sales of entertainment robots, including educational robotics kits jumped by 29 percent to around 1.7 million units. The entire segment is projected to increase to a total of 11 million units (2016-2019). The sales value adds up to around US\$ 9 billion in the same period.⁷ Robotics activities for STEM have been considered as interdisciplinary with a strong emphasis on collaborative learning, and robots have been perceived as a potentially powerful "vehicle" providing opportunities for construction, experimentation and collaboration between learners (Alimissis 2013). However, most of the robotics kits and activities tend to focus mainly on Programming and Engineering leaving aside the Mathematics and Science elements of STEM education. Additionally, in many educational robotics activities the element of construction and active exploration is limited as they are based on instructional, "step-by-step" type of exercises and closed quizzes. Nevertheless, the field of robotics bares an enormous educational potential as children's fascination for robots, along with the variety of fields and topics covered by robotics (Johnson, 2003), make robots a powerful idea to engage with, including gears and computers (Papert, 1980). At the same time, robotics is an excellent tool for teaching science and technology (Mataric, 2004; Mead 2012), therefore many educational robotics activities already focus on STEM (Baretto, 2012), which unfortunately attracts predominantly children who have not lost their interest in these subjects.

We do believe, however, that robots are a powerful tool for teaching STEM disciplines not only to the children who are already interested in those subjects. Thus, inspired by the spirit of the undergoing educational reform but also by the current state of educational robotics, involving mainly students with established interest in STEM, under the ER4STEM project, we undertook an

¹ Ordinance No 5 of 30.11.2015 on general education in force from 08.12.2015 issued by the Minister of Education and Science, obtained online in Bulgarian on March 10, 2018 at

http://zareformata.mon.bg/documents/nrdb5_30.11.2015_obshtoobr_podgotovka.pdf

² Educational curriculum for computer modelling for the third grade issued by the Minister of Education and Science, obtained online in Bulgarian on March 10, 2018 at https://www.mon.bg/upload/12205/UP_KM_3kl.pdf

³ Educational curriculum for computer modelling for the fourth grade issued by the Minister of Education and Science, obtained online in Bulgarian on March 10, 2018 at https://www.mon.bg/upload/13660/pr_UP_KM_4kl.pdf

⁴ Again in Ordinance No 5 of 30.11.2015 on general education in force from 08.12.2015 issued by the Minister of Education and Science, obtained online in Bulgarian on March 10, 2018 at

http://zareformata.mon.bg/documents/nrdb5_30.11.2015_obshtoobr_podgotovka.pdf

⁵ Guidelines for application for inclusion in the network of innovative schools in Bulgaria for the academic year 2018/2019, obtained online in Bulgarian on March 10, 2018 at https://www.mon.bg/upload/12192/Nasoki_2018_2019_iSchools.pdf

⁶ COUNCIL DECISION No 391 from 17 July 2017 on adopting a list of innovative schools for the academic year 2017/2018 (promulgated, SG No. 60/25 July 2017), obtained online in Bulgarian on March 10, 2018 at

https://www.mon.bg/upload/12193/rms_391_17072017.pdf

⁷ International Federation of Robotics, Press Release, Seoul, Oct 12, 2016, obtained online in English on March 10, 2018 at <https://ifr.org/ifr-press-releases/news/service-robotics>

exploration on how robotics activity plans could be designed to support teaching concepts, stipulated within an official mathematics curriculum. With the term activity plans, we refer to structured descriptions of robotics activities, which are built on the ER4STEM Activity Plan Template. This template provides a generic design tool that identifies critical elements of teaching and learning with robotics based in theory and practice and is expected to contribute to the description of effective learning and teaching with robotics (Yiannoutsou et al., 2017).

In this practice paper, we begin by introducing an activity plan, applied to a set of educational robotics workshops carried out between November and December 2016, within one public general education school in Sofia, Bulgaria. Each of the six 4th grade classes went through one educational workshop which comprised two 4-hour sessions. By involving experimentation with virtual and physical constructions within the activity, serving as tools of learning, we attempted to design an activity plan, which helps expand student's access to powerful ideas, in the sense of being immediately useful to the learner, by association to other productive ideas (Papert, 1980, 2000). We believe that this activity plan could be adapted to fit a variety of educational and cultural contexts and might be of use to educators looking for strategies to improve their student's involvement in subjects such as mathematics.

In addition to the pedagogic goals of this set of workshops, qualitative and quantitative data were collected through pre- and post-activity questionnaires completed by students (63 boys and 68 girls), and 6 groups of learners participated in semi-structured interviews to explore students' interactions and feedback. For the purposes of this paper, we will focus on data collected through questionnaires at the end of the workshops. The specific question we aimed to answer was what are Bulgarian students' attitudes towards constructionist robotics activities.

Finally, in this contribution we further share our experience with integrating collaborative work, aimed at developing an activity that could support the cultivation of some important 21st century skills within students (Dede, 2010), namely problem solving, collaboration, flexibility and adaptability.

Implementation Context

Overview

This activity plan was developed for boys and girls (age 9-11 years) studying at the 4th grade of one public general education school in Sofia, Bulgaria in 2016. The students have previously participated in educational robotics activities carried out by the implementation team and are expected to have previous experience programming with Scratch (however, previous programming knowledge was not required). They were also familiar with the collaboration requirements of the activity as well as the research protocol. This activity was developed following the guidelines of the Bulgarian national curriculum for mathematics for the 4th grade, thus knowledge of third grade mathematics was a prerequisite for the participation.

The educational robotics activities took place within regular school time. For each 4th grade class a separate workshop was organized, thus resulting in six workshops in total. Every workshop was of an eight-hour duration, with breaks, and was divided into two sessions of equal duration, with not more than one-week time between sessions. A regular school class in a public general education school in Bulgaria consists of anywhere within 24 and 28 students. Each session was led by 2-3 tutors.

Following our strong belief that the collaborative work plays a very important role for the effective engagement of students in the educational process, we apply the engagement theory (Kearsley & Shneiderman, 1998) as a significant part of the Constructionist teaching methods. Based also on their empirical conclusions that "technology can facilitate engagement in ways, difficult to achieve otherwise" (Kearsley & Shneiderman, 1998), we also asked students to assess their feelings on problem-based learning, working with robots and collaborative work.

Bulgaria's Mathematics Curriculum for the 4th Grade for General Education Schools

The fourth-grade curriculum in mathematics of Bulgaria⁸ is designed by the Ministry of Education in accordance to the State Educational Requirements and is developed in accordance to a set of principles, several of which served as a common ground for the design of the activity plan for the educational robotics workshops:

- Arithmetic operations with one and two-digit numbers and the properties of these actions;
- Deepening and expanding knowledge on the units of measurement by introducing angle measurement;
- Deepening and expanding the knowledge of the basic geometric shapes, types of triangles, types of angles, rectangle, square, knowledge of the circle and its elements
- Making evident how mathematics connects to subjects of other cultural and educational fields;
- Improving collaboration, communication, formulating and expressing ideas and cultivating skills such as observance, logical thinking, comparative thinking, critical analysis, formulating statements, making conclusions, experimentation;
- Develop interest and motivation to study mathematics and form a positive attitude towards the subject;

Following these guidelines, we created a multi-layered activity plan, to support the mission of the curriculum and possibly transfer this experience to fourth-grade mathematics educators, in order to contribute to the student's confidence in the subject and to inspire their curiosity in it.

Visualizing Mathematics with the MathBot

A Constructionist Activity Plan for Mathematical Experimentation

The educational robotics activities presented here are structured around the constructionist pedagogical approach, where the activity is organized around powerful ideas, facilitated through collaborative and group-centred games. Our focus was put on promoting a social dimension of robotics, which includes sharing personal knowledge and experiences on STEM related concepts while learning from others (Kafai & Burke, 2015). In this context, robotic construction and programming are seen as expressive medium to externalize ideas and thoughts, which through the sharing are becoming objects for discussion and change (Kynigos, 1995). Thus, all the activities are designed to take place in a common space and integrate virtual and physical constructions (Papert, 1980, 2000).

The pedagogical approach, as well as the background for the elaboration of the educational robotics workshops within the ER4STEM project are coordinated and structured with the means of an Activity Plan Template. This template was developed in the project as a design tool for planning robotics activities and depicts what we have identified as essential and transferrable elements of learning with robotics.

The Activity plan template, addresses the following aspects: a) Focus and resources: reference to the different domains involved, different types of objectives, duration and necessary material; b) contextual information regarding space and characteristics of the participants; c) social orchestration of the activity (i.e. group or individual work, formulation of groups etc.); d) a description of the teaching and learning procedures where the influence of the pedagogical theory is mostly demonstrated; e) expected student constructions; f) description of the sequencing and the focus of activities; g) means of evaluation (Yiannoutsou et al., 2017)

Social Orchestration and the Role of Discussion

The students were assigned to groups, each group consisting of 3-4 members. Every group was working around one table with one computer and one robot. We applied no specific grouping

⁸ Educational curriculum for mathematics for the fourth grade issued by the Minister of Education and Science, obtained online in Bulgarian on March 10, 2018 at https://www.mon.bg/upload/2645/matematika_4kl.pdf

criteria, as we wanted the students to be able to sit together based on pre-established friendships. We wanted students to be positively influenced by the idea that the workshops they were participating in were a fun group activity, which they could share with their friends.

As the students in one general education school class are about 25 boys and girls, this resulted in the formation of about 6-7 student groups in total.

Students were given discussion opportunities to reinforce their understanding by sharing with peers their constructions and working strategies. Students were supposed to verbally, and visually present their solutions to the tutors and the other teams, which required them to communicate their learning curve and solution in an understandable and clear manner. Student groups were encouraged to invite other student groups to present their solution and could go and ask for consultation with other student groups. By answering questions from other students and student groups, the presenting group was required to be able to explain their reasons and articulate their chosen strategy. The ability to clearly identify and communicate the reasoning underlying group decisions is at the core of the “thinking about one’s own thinking” (Han & Bhattacharya 2001) constructionist approach, which we aimed to integrate in our activity. Furthermore, in relation to the subject of mathematics itself, language can facilitate reflection and internal regulation, which is of importance to realize which parts of the mathematical idea are important (Hoyles, 1985).

Furthermore, we wanted our students to remain motivated to learn and participate throughout the activity. Motivation and understanding are shown to be increased when encouraged to explain knowledge (Brown, 1988). By enabling such discussions, the robot’s behaviour or the code is becoming a subject of common reflection, which empowers learning by providing the learner with an expertise to share.

To this end, apart from meaning generation we argue that constructionist robotics activities can also help the development of a number of 21st century skills including problem solving, flexibility and adaptability. With flexibility and adaptability, we refer to the abilities of a) incorporating feedback effectively, understanding, negotiating and balancing diverse views and beliefs to reach workable solutions and b) adapting to varied roles, schedules and context. In our workshops, we aim to reinforce these abilities through collaborative reflection, public discussion, role rotation and redistribution.

Implementation

For this particular set of workshops, we chose to use the Finch Robot, designed and developed by Birdbrain Technologies. Among the advantages of the Finch Robot is its cost-effectiveness, durability and the minimal amount of required knowledge or preparations in order to install all necessary software and run it. The Finch Robot is a black-box technology, equipped with many programmable sensors to support learning activities that emphasize programming the behaviour of the robot.

The Finch robot is programmable through the offline version of the visual programming language Scratch, which makes it highly accessible to students of this age group with little to no experience with programming and discrete logic. Furthermore, as Scratch allows the students to focus on tackling mathematical problems and easily create logical constructions, which becomes increasingly challenging with other, non-visual programming environments (Utting et al., 2010), where the focus falls on the code itself, thus making the programming process a purpose, instead of a tool for learning.

The activity plan was structured in seven phases of gradual complexity, apart from the first and the last one, which were introductory and evaluation-related. Every phase offered games with multiple sub-quests, which allowed for differentiation and made it possible for all groups to learn and problem-solve at their own pace. As cultural context, the activities were designed for Bulgarian students or students representing Bulgaria-based minorities and required fluency in Bulgarian language as game tasks are written in Bulgarian.

Phases 2 and 3 were more programming-oriented, allowing the students to reach a level of comfort in programming the robot and included basic command of the robot, programming it to perform a sequence of actions, programming its nose to blink in different colours while performing certain movements and others. Phase 4 included games related to drawing and measuring lines with the robot and rulers. In phase 5, students are engaged in a mathematical game of measuring the angle at which the robot turns with a protractor. Phase 6 aimed at exercising knowledge on the elements of a circle and included drawing circles with the robot and measuring its elements.

Ultimately, at the end of the workshop students gain understanding of what a robot is and know some common robotic parts. They understand that robots are programmable and gain knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors and are aware that different sensors serve different purpose. At the end of the workshop, students would have exercised basic age-appropriate concepts from the subject of mathematics.

The full activity plan, with more information about all phases is available at repository.er4stem.com.

Activity Evaluation

In order to be able to evaluate the activities and answer our research questions data was collected from students whose parents had given informed written consent. From 6 workshops held with different classes, data was obtained from 131 participants (63 boys and 68 girls). The majority of them had previously participated in educational robotics workshops in Bulgaria organized by the European Software Institute, under the ER4STEM project.

Quantitative data was obtained through pre and post workshop questionnaires. Interviews were conducted with one focus group from each class (6 interviews in total) and were transcribed, allowing more insight of the participants' experience and immediately after participating in the workshops. Additionally, reflections and observations were collected from tutors, along with student reflections and artefacts of learning.

This section presents the findings of the analysis of the questionnaires aims to provide insight on the participants' experience. It should be noted that some participants chose not to give an answer to some questions. Considering this, the percentage of students who left a question blank will be indicated next to the answers' report.

It is noteworthy to mention that this paper **will report on insights related to the implementation of the activity plan** focusing students' evaluation of their experience during the workshop. The activity's quantitative evaluation was carried out under the ER4STEM evaluation protocol, which is not specifically targeted at assessing student's understanding of mathematical concepts or student's attitude towards mathematic in general. The quantitative evaluation results reported below focus more, but not only on exploring boys and girls' interests in STEM, whether the approaches/activities appeal to them, on reporting on their intra-relational and interpersonal skills, and their feelings towards collaborative work experience.

Students' understanding of mathematical concepts, specifically for this activity, is qualitatively assessed through open answers in the questionnaires, focus group interviews, by collecting artefacts of learning, tutor observations and group reflections. The qualitative data obtained throughout ER4STEM workshops under analysis (May 2018) and will be reported on following the project.

What are Bulgarian students' attitude towards constructionist robotics activities?

The majority of the students who participated in the study reported the educational robotics workshop activities for mathematics as interesting, fun and not very difficult.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree Nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Blank
The problems we had to solve were:						
Interesting	1%	0%	2%	9%	88%	0%
Difficult	39%	20%	28%	8%	3%	0%
Fun	2%	0%	3%	10%	83%	0%
Working with robots was:						
Interesting	1%	0%	0%	8%	89%	0%
Difficult	42%	23%	22%	8%	5%	0%
Fun	2%	1%	0%	8%	89%	0%
Working in a team was:						
Interesting	3%	0%	8%	16%	71%	0%
Difficult	44%	22%	15%	8%	7%	0%
Fun	5%	1%	7%	16%	68%	0%

Figure 1 Aggregated students' feedback related to the problems solved, their work with robots and teamwork

Most students reported working in a team as interesting, fun and not difficult (Figure 1). Tutors' observation show that regardless of group conflicts that inevitably arose in some groups, the students generally manifested positive attitudes towards group work and felt excited for the opportunity to work in a team.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree Nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Blank
During the workshop...						
I solved a problem	9%	5%	23%	15%	45%	3%
I worked as part of a team	4%	2%	5%	14%	73%	2%
I programmed a robot	2%	1%	2%	4%	89%	2%
I was good at listening	2%	2%	15%	27%	50%	3%
I gave up quickly	80%	12%	3%	1%	3%	2%
I worked hard	3%	3%	8%	21%	64%	2%
I was bored	74%	12%	7%	5%	1%	2%
I helped someone	6%	2%	20%	24%	48%	1%

The students also gave a relatively high rating to the workshop they participated in with 4.93 stars out of 5.

Some students also reported increased confidence in mathematics and felt encouraged to participate in more activities such as this one.

Closing remarks

In this practice paper, we concentrated on providing insights on the design, implementation and pedagogical theory underlying an educational robotics activity, designed in support to the guidelines of a national educational curriculum in mathematics. We further provided aggregated feedback data reporting on students' experience with this activity, obtained by the primary school students who took part in the activities and we have given a brief overview on the evaluation protocol of the activities.

As practitioners in the field of educational robotics, we realize the importance of applying "powerful ideas" (Papert, 1980) as tools for learning. Through the Visualizing Mathematics with the MathBot activities, we aim to engage students in experimentation with digital and robotics artefacts to solve mathematical problems, in order to construct a better understanding of the interdisciplinary

application of mathematical concepts and to further develop a collaborative mind set to problem-solving. We believe that constructionist activities such as this one, bare the potential to enhance the properties of the linked curricula, and the possibility of adapting such activities to a plethora of robotics kits, programming environments and learning contexts makes this activity an idea worth sharing.

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